

Forecasting Credit Risk Systems of Consumers in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

this study critically analyzes factors (the macroeconomic indicators, credit policies, and regulations, and the behaviour of borrowers) that affect the credit risk system for Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) within the context of Saudi Arabia. This would help decision makers to have a reliable forecasting model that financial organizations can use to reduce credit losses. Data was extracted from a total of 48 SMEs companies. Data covered financial ratios of profitability, liquidity, solvency, Activity ratios, and other ratios related to log of total assets and log of total sales. After conducting logistic regression, and measures of KMO measure and Bartlett's test, the findings indicate that liquidity and activity ratios are significant factors that affect in predicting default risk. Furthermore, this study highlighted the requirement for a tailored credit risk assessment model for SMEs.

Key Words: Forecasting, Credit Risk, SMEs, Saudi Arabia

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Credit risk infers to the likelihood of a borrower failing to make their loan payments, and it is a vital element of financial management for lenders (Witzany, 2018). It is widely considered one of the primary risks faced by the banking sector, necessitating the adoption of effective and efficient credit risk management practices (Gupt & Sikarwar, 2020). The banking sector is primarily responsible for maximizing returns and providing the most significant value to investors through credit risk management. The banking sector plays a critical role in extending credit facilities and functioning as a catalyst for economic growth in every country, exerting a substantial effect on the economy. The financial system's reliability depends on the financial sector's performance, which is exposed to credit risk when a debtor fails to fulfil contractual agreements on the due date or at any time later.

Banks are primary suppliers of financial services, delivering services connected to credit, such as loans, payment facilities, and cash management. These services can be obtained from a bank. Credit expansion brings in significant revenue for financial institutions, but it also exposes those institutions to the possibility of financial loss. The banks are forced to do their business in the face of many unknowns, which puts them at risk for various financial and non-financial risks that jeopardize their performance, profitability, and reputation. In particular, credit risk plays a large influence on any bank's profitability; hence, banks' performance is more dependent on the precise measurement and effective management of this risk than any other risk. An increase in non-performing loans is one factor that adds to credit risk, and this factor alone may cause the demise of a bank. The substantial loss that could arise from borrowers not repaying their loans could lead to insolvency and financial catastrophes in the banking industry (Witzany, 2018). Both Kithinji (2010) and Kolapo et al. (2012) have argued that the rise in the number of loans that are considered to be non-performing significantly cuts into the profitability of banks.

The world's banks are the largest financial institutions and play an essential part in the growth of economies by providing funding for new business ventures, expanding existing ones, and producing new jobs (Khan et al., 2015). Nonetheless, a bank's operations expose it to various hazards, which necessitates the institution's participation in ongoing risk analysis and monitoring. According to Altunba and Marqués (2008), banks are exposed to a substantial number of risks, including liquidity risk, credit risk, and operational risk that may compromise their ability to continue existing and achieving success in the future. The probability of a loss in the financial market due to shifts in the values of various financial variables is what gives birth to the financial risk known as credit risk (Witzany, 2017). Borrowers' incapacity mostly causes this risk to satisfy their financial obligations and repay debts. According to Buchory (2015), non-performing loans are loans that do not meet industry standards and have an element of uncertainty. The NPL ratio is an indicator of the quality of the bank's management of its loans. A larger ratio indicates that the quality of loan management is lower, raising the likelihood that a bank is experiencing difficult conditions.

1.2 Problem Statement

In recent years, SMEs and individuals have been more likely to use credit to fulfil various demands, which has led to a considerable increase in money generated by banks and other financial institutions. According to Alma'alli (2019), the use of credit in a responsible manner can make a positive contribution to the economy. In contrast, the use of credit in an irresponsible manner can bring economic damage and disruption. The quantity of overdue credit globally has doubled since 2008, and credit choices are still being made regularly. However, van Thiel & van Raaij (2019) opined that the underlying causes of the credit crisis that occurred in 2008 have not been remedied. Financial institutions must conduct credit application reviews utilising scientific methodologies to reduce credit risks and avert economic and social damage. According to Alma'alli (2019), to accurately predict risk-based credit scores, algorithms have been developed that use various criteria and models.

In Saudi Arabia, the banking sector is categorised into two types: Islamic banks, comprising Islamic banks, and conventional banks, consisting of nine banks. The Saudi Arabia Monetary Agency (SAMA) monitors and regulates this sector. As in many other countries, credit risk management is a critical factor in ensuring the stability and efficiency of the financial sector in the KSA. Given the substantial effect of credit risk on the overall financial system, the prediction of credit risk systems of SMEs is a vital task for financial institutions in Saudi Arabia.

This study seeks to provide an in-depth analysis of credit risk systems for SMEs in Saudi Arabia and to develop a reliable forecasting model that financial institutions can use to minimize credit losses. The research aims to investigate the factors affecting credit risk in Saudi Arabia, including the macroeconomic indicators, credit policies, and regulations, as well as the behaviour of borrowers.

2. Literature Review

It is essential to manage financial risks effectively to sustain new energy enterprises in Saudi Arabia. These risks include credit risk, a significant risk factor that new energy firms need to manage effectively. Banks and other financial institutions consider new energy firms a high-risk business, increasing the cost of borrowing and thereby reducing the firms' borrowing capacity (Shalaby, 2004). Therefore, new energy enterprises should have sound financial records and stable cash flows to enhance their creditworthiness. Furthermore, effective management of market risk is also critical in new energy enterprises. Market risk is associated with the fluctuation of energy prices and market demand, affecting the enterprises' revenue (Zamberi-Ahmad, 2012). New energy firms can reduce this risk by adopting hedging strategies to lock in prices and diversify their customer base.

Additionally, operational and liquidity risks also pose a significant challenge to new energy firms. For example, operational risk can result in delays in project delivery and cost overruns, leading to losses. On the other hand, liquidity risk can lead to cash flow problems, affecting the firm's ability to meet its financial obligations (Shalaby, 2004). Therefore, new energy firms must adopt effective risk management strategies to mitigate these risks and enhance their financial sustainability.

Assessing the likelihood of a default is an essential part of credit risk management since it relates to the possibility of suffering a financial loss due to the incapacity of consumers to meet the terms and conditions of their credit agreements (Witzany, 2018). The procedure for making decisions on credit risk has been significantly influenced by the increasing prevalence of automated processes and technological breakthroughs (Anderson, 2007). Credit risk management can create quick choices that can be relied upon by automating processes and quantifying risk estimates. This reduces the number of unnecessary bureaucratic phases (Abdou & Pointon, 2011). In the past, choices were made using more subjective methods due to the lack of availability of credit scoring systems and automation technology. This method examined applicants based on various criteria, including their character, financial resources, collateral, capacity, and condition. On the other hand, this method had several significant drawbacks, including a capacity that was insufficient to handle a high number of applications, a susceptibility to incorrect classification, and an inaccurate nature (Dastile et al., 2020).

In the credit industry, information asymmetry is a common problem whereby the borrowers possess more information regarding their potential to repay loans than lenders (Kabari & Nwachukwu, 2013). This information gap leads to lenders facing uncertainty about a borrower's creditworthiness, resulting in difficulties in credit risk assessment. Therefore, to address this issue, quantifying risk assessment is necessary, as it helps reduce the information asymmetry gap between borrowers and lenders. Digital risk management is one of the effective ways to mitigate the problem of information asymmetry, as it enables lenders to gather data from various sources. By collating and analysing data, lenders can make more informed decisions, reducing their reliance on data provided by borrowers. This, in turn, reduces the information gap between borrowers and lenders, thus facilitating better credit risk assessment. Moreover, with technological advances, decision support systems such as artificial intelligence (AI) have become more sophisticated (Abedin et al., 2018). These systems use machine learning algorithms and statistical techniques to identify and analyse patterns in data. AI can thus help to establish robust credit risk assessment models by identifying predictor factors that can distinguish between good and bad credit risks. In recent years, the credit industry has relied on the construction of classifiers for prediction, which are crucial for establishing decision support systems for credit risk assessment. Classifiers are models that use a set of input variables to predict the likelihood of a specific outcome. For credit risk assessment, classifiers can be used to predict the probability of default or the likelihood of a borrower repaying their loan on time.

Historically, the most prevalent method for assessing credit risk has focused on financial and demographic data. Yet, the absence of financial history information for some applicants has led to the development of new approaches for estimating the likelihood of default. Much research has investigated the link between socioeconomic and behavioural characteristics and the likelihood of defaulting on a loan (Pedro et al., 2015). Also, the influence of personality factors on default and repayment behaviour has been examined. Many characteristics highly connected with default probability have prompted the quest for new source of data that offer more insights into the consumer's characterise personality (Pedro et al., 2015).

The COVID-19 pandemic forced radical changes to e-commerce such as the digitization of many traditional brick-and-mortar stores (Wertz, 2020). Moreover, Wang et al. (2013) wrote that e-commerce switched from using money transfers to using credit transfers to pay thus making credit risk management an important part of e-commerce. Peer-to-peer and online retail lending have grown a lot in recent years, hurting credit portfolio quality (van Thiel & van Raaij, 2019). Since online transactions can happen in a matter of seconds, big changes can happen quickly. The present-day credit management landscape is characterised by the inability to update traditional credit management indicators in real-time, a situation which has led to the exploration of alternative methods to measure credit risk. The limitations of financial indicators, which are unable to provide an accurate and timely depiction of an applicant's credit status, have necessitated the search for new approaches to supplement the conventional indicators. This position is consistent with the assertion made by BJORKEGREN and GRISSIN (2018) who argued that traditional credit management indicators are static and do not provide a real-time picture of a person's credit status. The situation is further compounded by the scarcity of data and credit bureaus, especially in developing countries, thus requiring the need for non-financial predictors to provide a comprehensive evaluation of an individual's creditworthiness. As noted by Wang et al. (2013), non-financial predictors are important in supplementing traditional credit management indicators in order to present a more accurate and up-to-date picture of a person's creditworthiness.

According to Onay & Oztürk (2018), the usage of big data is currently undergoing a transformation that is significantly impacting the credit scoring industry. Whereas the utilization of big data can result in more accurate credit scoring algorithms, it also raises concerns over the confidentiality and safety of user information. Existing rules provide insufficient protection for scores derived from big data, one of the criticisms levelled against them. Moreover, steps need to be implemented to prevent the misclassification of applications to avoid stigmatisation. Rules are required to guarantee that these new credit scoring systems will provide ratings of credit risk that are both objective and accurate (Citron & Pasquale, 2014). The issue of "lack of transparency" was also considered a serious privacy concern by King & Forder (2016). Because of the need to maintain business secrecy, organisations do not give applicants transparent information regarding how they process data. This results in an information gap between organisations and applicants.

The application of data analytics makes it possible to unearth previously concealed personal information, which may then be used in the profiling process. Because of the personal information that can be used to identify them, customers risk having their identities stolen and being victims of fraudulent activity (King & Forder, 2016).

According to Louzis et al. (2012), banks subscribing to this perspective are more likely to take on excessive risk, such as lending to borrowers with lower creditworthiness and maintaining a high leverage ratio. According to Saunders et al. (1990), the correlation between the size of a bank and its level of risk ought to be negative. This is because larger banks have a more diversified asset base, which helps to limit risk. In a study looking at Islamic finance and risk, How et al. (2005) discovered that larger banks in Malaysia exhibited a considerably lower credit risk than smaller banks. This was the finding from Malaysia. In a similar vein, Gulati et al. (2019) found that the size of India's banks has an impact on the country's credit risk. They observed that larger banks have greater exposure to the risks associated with individual companies since these banks give financing to a wider variety of companies, which results in greater credit risk. In addition, the size of banks is one factor that contributes to mitigating the adverse consequences of economic crises. Abdelrahim (2013) discovered that the size of Saudi banks had a significant inverse correlation with their credit risk during 2008 Global Financial Crisis. This finding suggests that larger banks have lower credit risk because they have a broader asset base. A similar finding was found by Beck et al. (2013), who stated that during the GFC, a significant negative link existed between size and the percentage of non-performing loans held by conventional and Islamic banks.

3. Methodology

This research evaluates credit risk for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Saudi Arabia using a logistic regression model based on factor analysis. The model considers both non-defaulters and defaulters, as including both is necessary for accurate credit risk modeling. The study follows three principles to assess SME credit risk in Saudi Arabia, identifying financial factors to determine independent variables. Kanapickiene and Spicas (2019) highlight the importance of including good and bad debtors in credit risk modelling for accurate results.

The study aims to develop a model for evaluating credit risk in SMEs through logistic regression techniques, using principal components extracted through factor analysis as predictor variables and credit risk as the dependent variable. To reduce the number of factors, dimension reduction via factor analysis will be employed. By using principal components as explanatory variables, relationships between independent variables will be eliminated, and the model's prediction accuracy improved. This approach enhances the accuracy of the model's predictions by reducing the number of explanatory variables.

This study uses various financial ratios from prior research, grouped into categories such as profitability, liquidity, and solvency. Only variables with less than 20% missing data are included in the analysis. The data is collected from the Saudi stock exchange market, and time-variant and firm size factors are used as control variables to address indigeneity issues. The study emphasizes the importance of including control variables to improve the accuracy of the credit risk model. The table below shows the ratios used:

Table 3.1 Financial ratios used for the study

Profitability	Gross sales
	Gross profits/Total assets
	Current assets/current liabilities
	Net profits/Equity
Liquidity ratios	Cash/Current liabilities
	(Current liabilities –cash)/total assets
	Working capital/total assets
Solvency ratios	Total assets/Total liabilities
	Equity/Total assets

	Current assets/(T. liabilities-cash)
Activity ratios	Inventory/sales
	Sales/Cash
	Equity/Sales
	Working capital/ Sales
Other ratios	Log of Total assets
	Log of Total sales

This study examines the credit risk of SMEs in Saudi Arabia using a logistic regression model based on factor analysis. A sample of 48 SMEs with available financial data is included in the analysis. Factor analysis is conducted to identify potential correlations between variables, and logistic regression is used to predict credit risk. The resulting variable is either non-default or default. Purposive sampling is used due to the limited availability of financial data from SMEs in Saudi Arabia. The model is written as:

$$Probability\ of\ default = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

$$z = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k$$

The forward regression method is used, gradually adding independent variables that are strongly correlated with the dependent variable while eliminating insignificant ratios. The model must comply with specific requirements, including a chi-square criterion with a p-value less than 0.05 and significant values for Wald's p-value. Additionally, the Cox and Snell's and Nagelkerke's R2 should range from 0 to 1 and ensures compliance with requirements proposed by Kanapickiene & Spicas (2019) and Field (2013).

4. Results and Discussion

To ensure the suitability of factor analysis, an applicability test is conducted to examine the correlations between initial variables. The KMO and Bartlett's tests are commonly used, and if KMO is higher than 0.5 and Bartlett's test probability value is below 0.05, factor analysis is considered suitable. The KMO and Bartlett tests results are presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: The KMO and Bartlett tests results

Test		Measure
KMO Measure		0.582
Bartlett's tests	Approximate Chi square	11428.6
	Degrees of freedom	240
	P value	0.000

KMO test value is higher than 0.5 thresholds indicating suitability for factor analysis. Bartlett's test indicates a strong association between the variables, making it appropriate to extract principal components using dimension reduction.

Table 3.3: Community values for the variables which measure effectiveness of the PCA

Variable	Initial value	Extraction value
Gross sales	1	0.768
Gross profits/Total assets	1	0.855
Current assets/current liabilities	1	0.911

Net profits/Equity	1	0.826
Cash/Current liabilities	1	0.771
(Current liabilities –cash)/total assets	1	0.928
Working capital/total assets	1	0.886
Total assets/Total liabilities	1	0.849
Equity/Total assets	1	0.854
Current assets/(T. liabilities-cash)	1	0.930
Inventory/sales	1	0.873
Sales/Cash	1	0.888
Equity/Sales	1	0.917
Working capital/ Sales	1	0.860
Log of Total assets	1	0.763
Log of Total sales	1	0.766

Table 3.3 presents the communalities of variables, which indicate the effectiveness of the PCA in reducing dimensions. Higher communalities suggest greater efficiency of the test, and the majority of variables have communalities over 70%, indicating the extracted components held superior explanatory power and unique information about the examined variables. To determine the common factors representative of the initial information contained in the variables, the PCA method uses the initial eigenvalue as an auxiliary criterion and the cumulative variance percentage of contribution as the reference value (Field, 2013). Principal components with eigenvalues greater than one are extracted, and those with a cumulative variance percentage of contribution equal to or greater than 70% are considered representative. The first five components have a cumulative variance percentage of contribution over 70.8%, indicating that less than 30% of the initial variable information is lost, and the principal components extracted from the analysis represent much information about the variables. Detailed information can be obtained from the appendix.

The PCA method is utilized to extract principal components from the initial variables, which decreases their intercorrelations and reflects most of the initial data. Nonetheless, it is difficult to determine the key factors based on the initial extracted component matrix. Therefore, the VARIMAX model is applied to perform an orthogonal rotation that simplifies the correlation between each initial factor and the extracted principal. Variables that load higher on the principal component have a stronger correlation with the initial variable. The components are then considered to be a representation of the grouping of the financial ratios when running the model.

To determine the principal components that should be included in the logistic regression model, scores are derived from Table 3.4. PC1, PC3, and PC5 are removed from the model as they have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating they do not affect the defaulting of Saudi Arabian SMEs.

Table 3.4: Removed variables from the model

	Variable	Score	Degrees of freedom	P value
Step 1	PC1	1.963	1	0.159
	PC3	1.332	1	0.248
	PC5	2.954	1	0.080
	Overall Statistics	6.249	3	0.169

Therefore, only PC2 and PC 4 are considered in the logistic regression. Table 3.5 shows the logistic model estimation results, which include only two significant independent variables, PC2 and PC4. The pseudo-R2 for step 1 is 0.117, indicating good variation in the dependent variable while that for step 2 is 0.194. The suitability of using the logistic regression for risk estimation models is tested using the Hosmer-Lemeshow (HL) test, which assesses the goodness of fit between the data and the model.

Table 3.5: Results of the logistic model estimation

Variable		Standard error	P value	Log likelihood	Cox and Snell R2	Pseudo R2
Step 1	PC2	-1.823	0.467	173.88	0.074	0.138
	constant	0.552	0.153			
Step 2	PC2	-1.779	0.413	132.11	0.061	0.194
	PC4	-0.937	0.612			
	Constant	1.113	0.099			

The results of the HL test are shown in Table 3.6 below:

Table 3.6: Results of the HL test

Step	Chi-square	P value
1	14.740	0.064
2	19.663	0.082

From the table above, the model is fitting the data in both steps with a p value >0.05 showing the model to be appropriate. We then perform the classification using the values obtained from the logistic model to highlight the percentage that explains the data for both step 1 and step 2 as shown in table 3.7 below with the cut value being 0.5:

Table 3.7: Model classification results

		Observed		Predicted credit rating	
				Default	% Correct
Step 1	Credit rating	No default	24	48	36.4
		Default	12	99	87.5
	Overall rating				71.8
Step 2	Credit rating	No default	26	43	36.8
		Default	10	102	90.8
	Overall rating				77.3

The overall rating for step 1 was 71.8% while that for step 2 was 77.3% which shows the model did a decent job of classifying the default rates of the SMEs based on the data. The final logistic equation that can be used to model the results can be expressed as:

$$Probability\ of\ default = \frac{1}{1 + e^{1.13 - 1.779PC2 - 0.937PC4}}$$

The analysis concludes that the most significant factors influencing the defaulting of Saudi Arabian SMEs are the liquidity and activity ratios, which are calculated using current liabilities, cash, total assets, working capital, inventories, sales and total assets in accordance with Table 3.1. These ratios reflect an SME's ability to settle its current liabilities by using its quick assets, and they were identified using PCA and logistic regression models.

The SME sector, particularly in emerging countries like Saudi Arabia, is often characterized by information opacity, which can lead to biases in credit risk assessments. To address this challenge, the proposed model evaluates the probability of default of an SME based on its liquidity and activity ratios, thereby providing valuable information to governments and financial institutions. It is widely recognized that default

prediction models employed by financial institutions for large corporations may not be suitable for SMEs, and using such models for SMEs may lead to poor performance.

This study highlights the importance of implementing regulations to ensure that new credit scoring systems provide accurate and objective ratings of credit risk similar to the study by Citron & Pasquale (2014). The issue of lack of transparency in data availability, which is a concern was identified by King and Forder (2016) and it was observed in the study as well. This underscores the importance of employing appropriate tools that account for the peculiarities of SMEs in credit risk evaluation. Specifically, financial institutions should use specific risk assessment models that take into account the limited financial information provided by SME managers to avoid bias in assessing the probability of default. An important policy implication that emerges from this analysis is that financial institutions should separate credit risk assessments for large corporations and SMEs, and should employ a version of the proposed model that is tailored to the features of small and medium-sized enterprises depending on the regulatory environment in each country.

5. Conclusion

Based on the analysis of liquidity and activity ratios, the study found that the SMEs liquidity and activity ratios, were the most influential factors in predicting default risk. The study also highlighted the need for tailored credit risk assessment models for SMEs, which take into account the peculiarities of these businesses and avoid bias in the probability of default.

The study presents a simple statistical model that can be used by creditors to evaluate the credit risk of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in emerging and frontier markets. The model is constructed using factor analysis with the principal component method and logistic regression, and it produces a score representing the probability of SMEs defaulting on loans. Even individuals without prior statistical or information technology knowledge can easily interpret the model's outcome. The data required for the model is readily available, as most SMEs submit financial statements every year, and their financial data can be accessed by banks. Financial ratios and their trends, calculated for different periods, provide crucial information about the credit health status of SMEs, and the SMEs' liquidity and activity ratios can help predict their future solvency. Therefore, this study's model can be an effective tool for creditors to assess the creditworthiness of SMEs in emerging and frontier markets.

Finally, the study emphasized the importance of ensuring transparency and accuracy in credit scoring systems, as well as protecting the privacy of applicants from potential identity theft and fraudulent activity.

6. References

- Abdelrahim, Khalil Elian. 2013. Effectiveness of Credit Risk Management of Saudi Banks in the Light of Global Financial Crisis: A Qualitative Study. *Asian Transaction on Basic and Applied Sciences* 3: 73–91.
- Abdou, H., Pointon, J., & El-Masry, A. (2008). Neural nets versus conventional techniques in credit scoring in Egyptian banking. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 35(3), 1275–1292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2007.08.030>
- Abedin, M. Z., Guotai, C., Colombage, S., & Moula, F. (2018). Credit default prediction using a support vector machine and a probabilistic neural network. *The Journal of Credit Risk*, 14(2),1–27. <https://doi.org/10.21314/jcr.2017.233>
- Agwu, E. (2018). Credit Risk Management: Implications on Bank Performance and Lending Growth. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3122501>
- Ahsan, M. K. (2017). A Comparison of Job Satisfaction of Private and Public Banks' Employees. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*. <https://doi.org/http://edupediapublications.org/journals/index.php/JSMaP/>
- Alma Ç allı, B. (2019). *A psychometric and financial factors based framework suggestion for an integrated credit risk assessment information system* (Sakarya University). Sakarya University. <https://acikerisim.sakarya.edu.tr/handle/20.500.12619/68672>

- Altunbaş, Y., & Marqués, D. (2008). Mergers and acquisitions and bank performance in Europe: The role of strategic similarities. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 3, 204–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconbus.2007.02.003>
- Anderson, R. (2007). *The credit scoring toolkit*. Oxford University Press Inc.
- Beck, Thorsten, Asli Demirgüç-Kunt, and Ouarda Merrouche. 2013. Islamic vs. Conventional Banking: Business Model, Efficiency and Stability. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 37: 433–47.
- Bjorkegren, D., & Grissen, D. (2018). Behavior revealed in mobile phone usage predicts loan repayment. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2611775>
- Ciampi, F., Giannozzi, A., Marzi, G., & Altman, E. I. (2021). Rethinking SME default prediction: A systematic literature review and future perspectives. *Scientometrics*, 126, 2141–2188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03856-0>
- Citron, D. K., & Pasquale, F. (2014). The scored society: Due process for automated predictions. *Washington Law Review*, 89(1), 1–33. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2376209>
- Dastile, X., Celik, T., & Potsane, M. (2020). Statistical and machine learning models in credit scoring: A systematic literature survey. *Applied Soft Computing*, 91, 106263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106263>
- Gulati, Rachita, Anju Goswami, and Sunil Kumar. 2019. What drives credit risk in the Indian banking industry? An empirical investigation. *Economic Systems* 43: 42–62.
- Gupta, M., & Sikarwar, T. S. (2020). Modelling credit risk management and bank's profitability. *International Journal of Electronic Banking*, 2, 170. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijebank.2020.109663>
- How, Janice C. Y., Melina Abdul Karim, and Peter Verhoeven. 2005. Islamic Financing and Bank Risks: The Case of Malaysia. *Thunderbird International Business Review* 47: 75–94.
- Kabari, L. G., & Nwachukwu, E. O. (2013). Decision support system using decision tree and neural networks. *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems*, 4(7), 8–20.
- King, N. J., & Forder, J. (2016). Data analytics and consumer profiling: Finding appropriate privacy principles for discovered data. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 32(5), 696–714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clsr.2016.05.002>
- Kithinji, A. M. (2010). Credit risk management and profitability of Commercial banks in Kenya. *University of Nairobi*. <https://doi.org/http://hdl.handle.net/11295/40437>
- Louzada, F., Ara, A., & Fernandes, G. B. (2016). Classification methods applied to credit scoring: Systematic review and overall comparison. *Surveys in Operations Research and Management Science*, 21(2), 117–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sorms.2016.10.001>
- Louzis, Dimitrios P., Angelos T. Vouldis, and Vasilios L. Metaxas. 2012. Macroeconomic and bank-specific determinants of non-performing loans in Greece: A comparative study of mortgage, business and consumer loan portfolios. *Journal of Banking & Finance* 36: 1012–27
- Ntwiga, D. B. (2016). *Social network analysis for credit risk modeling*. University of Nairobi.
- Onay, C., & Öztürk, E. (2018). A review of credit scoring research in the age of Big Data. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 26(3), 382–405. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfrc-06-2017-0054>
- Pedro, J. S., Proserpio, D., & Oliver, N. (2015). MobiScore: Towards universal credit scoring from mobile phone data. In: F. Ricci, K. Bontcheva, O. Conlan, & S. Lawless (Eds.), *User modeling, adaptation and personalization. UMAP 2015* (Vol. 9146). Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-20267-9_16

- Samet, A. (2020). *Global ecommerce market report: ecommerce sales trends and growth statistics for 2021*. <https://www.businessinsider.com/global-ecommerce-2020-report>
- Saunders, Anthony, Elizabeth Strock, and Nickolaos G. Travlos. 1990. Ownership Structure, Deregulation, and Bank Risk Taking. *Journal of Finance* 45: 643–54
- Shalaby, N. (2004). SMEs development in Saudi Arabia. *Eastern Province Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia*, 3.
- Tounsi, Y., Hassouni, L., & Anoun, H. (2017). Credit scoring in the age of big data – A state-of-the-art. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*, 15(7), 134–145.
- van Thiel, D., & van Raaij, W. F. F. (2019). Artificial intelligent credit risk prediction: An empirical study of analytical artificial intelligence tools for credit risk prediction in a digital era. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 19(8), 150–170.
- Wang, Y., Li, S., & Lin, Z. (2013, July 17–19). *Revealing key non-financial factors for online credit-scoring in e-financing* [Conference session]. 2013 10th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management—Proceedings of ICSSSM 2013, pp. 547–552. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icsssm.2013.6602651>
- Wertz, J. (2020). *3 Emerging E-Commerce Growth Trends to Leverage in 2020*. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jiawertz/2020/08/01/3-emerging-e-commerce-growth-trends-to-leverage-in-2020/?sh=7d72c77b6fee>
- Witzany, J. (2018). *Credit Risk Management: Pricing, Measurement, and Modeling*. Springer.
- Zamperi-Ahmad, S. (2012). Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises development in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Problems and constraints. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 8(4), 217-232. <https://doi.org/10.1108/20425961211276606>

APPENDIX

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction sums of square Loadings			Rotation sums of square Loadings		
	Total	% variance	Cumulative % variance	Total	% variance	Cumulative % variance	Total	% variance	Cumulative % variance
1	6.349	19.333	19.333	6.349	19.333	19.333	5.748	17.731	17.731
2	5.561	17.849	37.182	5.561	17.849	37.182	5.183	16.849	34.580
3	4.877	15.359	52.541	4.877	15.359	52.541	4.146	16.119	50.699
4	3.665	11.118	63.659	3.665	11.118	63.659	2.995	9.118	59.817
5	2.451	7.237	70.896	2.451	7.237	70.896	2.359	11.079	70.896
6	1.779	6.687	77.583						
7	1.223	6.158	83.741						
8	0.972	5.008	88.749						
9	0.851	4.741	93.490						
10	0.779	2.672	96.162						
11	0.618	1.512	97.674						
12	0.439	0.904	98.578						
13	0.338	0.752	99.330						
14	0.299	0.388	99.718						
15	0.257	0.165	99.883						
16	0.193	0.112	99.995						
17	0.144	0.003	99.998						
18	0.098	0.002	100.000						